

Latent Autoimmune Diabetes of Adulthood (LADA): A Commonly Misdiagnosed Condition as Type II Diabetes Mellitus

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Abstract

While the awareness of Latent Autoimmune Diabetes of Adults (LADA) is growing, many of these individuals are still misdiagnosed as having Type II diabetes mellitus. Even though current treatment patterns may be similar, an autoimmune etiology may require a paradigm shift in the treatment protocol utilized for these patients. Biologic agents used against Rheumatoid Arthritis have also been proved to be effective against diabetes mellitus. The growing number of peer-reviewed articles in the professional literature is an indication of how individuals in the scholastic arena are expanding in the current body of knowledge. By dissemination of best practices, other health care practitioners can learn about the specific needs of this specific subgroup of patients with diabetes. The purpose of the literature review conducted here was to describe the status of the peer-reviewed literature over the past decade pertaining to LADA and raise awareness on biologic agent treatment methods that may be more appropriate than what is currently utilized. A literature search was conducted using the Cochrane, Medline, and PubMed daases. Inclusion criteria included publication date from January 1, 2006 through July 31, 2015, written in the English language, and a focus on Latent Autoimmune Diabetes of Adults as the primary discipline. Diabetes was searched as an overarching discipline; articles focused on sub-disciplines or other health professions disciplines were excluded. The search resulted in 235 articles. Each of the authors reviewed the abstracts for all articles and read full articles when necessary. The result was 10 articles that were then considered in depth. The articles were categorized according to their primary theme: interventions (N=2); pathophysiology (N=3); case study (N=2); LADA versus Type II Diabetes (N=3). Year of publication and journal were also examined. The results of the literature search lead to several observations about how the peer-reviewed literature has been used to date and how it could be used to advance the emerging field of diagnosis and treatment of LADA. Additionally, the autoimmune component of LADA could be used to change scientists' thinking about Type 2 Diabetes as well.

Keywords

Latent Autoimmune Diabetes of Adults, Diabetes Mellitus, Type 1.5 Diabetes, Autoimmune, Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus

1. Introduction

Type II Diabetes Mellitus is on the rise globally and characterized by a profound level of insulin resistance and considered to have a genetic predilection [1-2]. Patients with Latent Autoimmune Diabetes of Adults (LADA) have a more insidious onset, and the disorder is characterized by an autoimmune attack of insulin-producing beta cells of the pancreas, which are considered foreign. In 2005, LADA was

defined as adult age of onset, presence of autoantibodies, and insulin after at least six months of diagnosis [2]. The World Health Organization (WHO) classified LADA under Type 1 Diabetes because patients become insulin dependent after six months. Due to this definition, 12% of all adult-onset diabetes is considered to be LADA [3]. Glutamic Acid Decarboxylase is an enzyme with the role of breaking down glutamate to carbon dioxide and gamma amino butyric acid (GABA). Glutamic Acid Decarboxylase Autoantibody (GADA) is an indicator for LADA. More specifically GAD₆₅ has been administered in the

past to successfully treat Type 1 Diabetes [4].

2. Diagnosis and Treatment of LADA

With traditionally according to Lutgens et al. clinical features hold evidence-based credibility in order to exclusively categorize diabetes patients with a specific diagnosis, other factors might need to be taken into consideration [5]. Other researchers have presented contradictory evidence regarding the occurrence of LADA [6]. Recent studies have demonstrated without a doubt that there is a bimodal distribution of GADA titers in LADA [6-7]. Due to the variations in GADA, there are two distinct subgroups of patients with distinct clinical, autoimmune, and genetic features can be identified. Out of the two subgroups, there is one with high GADA titers who tend to be younger, lower BMI, and a lower prevalence of metabolic syndrome⁷⁻⁸. These individuals have similar traits of insulin deficiency like higher A1C, lower C-peptide, and a profile of more severe/extended autoimmunity (higher prevalence of other diabetes specific or other autoimmune disease [thyroid peroxidase] autoantibodies) than individuals with lower GADA titers. Polyglandular autoimmune syndrome may have some overlap with the occurrence of LADA [8-9].

Varying titer of LADA patients is indicative of the heterogeneity existing within this condition. Those patients with multiple and high autoantibody titers resemble those with type 1 diabetes in various features, whereas individuals with single and low autoantibodies titers resemble those with type 2 diabetes [10-11]. It might also have therapeutic implications, since different approaches may be applied to the two groups. Apart from GADA, there are other autoantibodies that have potential use in diagnosis. Islet cell autoantibody (ICA), insulinoma-associated (IA-2) autoantibody, and zinc transporter autoantibody (ZnT8) are all excellent biomarkers which can aid in diagnosis in the latter subgroup described [11].

3. Non-Traditional and Biologic Therapies for LADA

Even though sulfonylureas are traditionally very effective for diabetes by increasing insulin released from beta cells, these drugs are ineffective against LADA. A one-year randomized control trial comparing insulin versus insulin and glibenclamide (sulfonylurea) in those with LADA showed that those subjects exclusively taking insulin had better outcomes [11-12]. Not only was there better metabolic control for the insulin-exclusive group, but there was also less ICA and GADA after one year. Similarly, a study examining the effect of adding insulin to sulfonylureas and of withdrawal of sulfonylureas on glycemic control in type 2 diabetic patients seemed to support the exclusion of sulfonylureas in autoantibody-positive subjects, who were less likely to respond to it.

While traditional medications have shown promising results, a paradigm shift needs to be made to understand the

effect of inflammation. Consequently biologic agents may work better than the traditional diabetes medications. Traditional randomized control trials have demonstrated how sulfonylureas are ineffective. Some biologic disease-modifying antirheumatic drugs (DMARDs) have shown promising results associated with diabetes. Mastrandrea et al. found through a randomized, placebo-controlled, double-blind study that etanercept is a potentially effective treatment against Type 1 diabetes, and this treatment can be extrapolated to LADA [13]. In a case study, researchers found infliximab successfully control diabetes [14]. Yazdani-Biuki and colleagues demonstrated how prolonged use of infliximab can cause a therapeutic side effect of higher insulin sensitivity [15]. As seen with the effect of etanercept in this patient, one patient was able to cease taking insulin therapy and found remission from diabetes. Repeated case reports of hypoglycemic states and increased glucose tolerance demonstrates the therapeutic potential of TNF- α inhibitors in diabetes [16]. On the molecular level, through mouse models, TNF- α is known to downregulate GLUT-4 in adipose tissue. Specifically, GLUT-4 is a transporter which allows for uptake of glucose into adipose tissue which is one mechanism through which glycemic control is achieved. Additionally, TNF- α is known to be associated with Toll-like Receptors 2 and 4 and cytokines like interleukin-6. Additionally, heat shock protein (DiaPep277) was shown to shift the dominance from T-helper-1 to T-helper-2[17]. These findings have potential genetic and molecular implications in monitoring and treating diabetes disease levels through immunomodulation [6].

Table 1. Review of Most Important Articles on LADA.

Author/Year	Research Objectives	Findings from the study and implications on LADA
Huang et al. (2013) [11]	The role of Zinc transporter 8 autoantibody (ZnT8A).	ZnT8A can be used to differentiate between LADA and Type II Diabetes Mellitus
Ipadeola et al. (2015) [18]	To investigate the frequency and characteristics of persons with latent autoimmune diabetes in adults (LADA) amongst patients who had been clinically diagnosed as type 2 diabetes mellitus	No clinical differences were found between LADA and Type II Diabetes Mellitus, making GAD antibody testing even more important
Brophy et al. (2011) [2]	To compare interventions used for LADA.	The review demonstrates that insulin treatment may be preferable compared to sulphonylurea treatment but there is little evidence regarding other forms of treatment.
Maddaloni et al. (2015) [19]	To describe and to characterize clinical features of latent autoimmune diabetes in adults (LADA) compared to type 1 and type 2 diabetes in the UAE.	Agreement with previous data from European and Asian population and also support the “end of the rainbow” Hypothesis. Different subtypes of adult-onset diabetes are not completely distinct diseases, but they form a of varying immune

Author/Year	Research Objectives	Findings from the study and implications on LADA
Liu et al. (2015) [20]	To investigate the relationship between GAD autoantibody (GADA) titers and changing of β -cell function in patients with latent autoimmune diabetes in adults (LADA).	LADA patients with a low GADA titer had metabolic phenotypes and loss of β -cell function similar to type 2 diabetic patients.
Porcel Chacon et al. (2015) [21]	Case report of LADA in a younger patient	Case report demonstrating that LADA is possible in the pediatric population
Aycan et al. (2004) [22]	Case report of LADA in a child	8-year old female with GADA positive titer, autoimmune thyroiditis, and celiac disease
Chen et al. (2010)[23]	The role of thioredoxin interacting protein in diabetes (TXNIP)	Lack of TXNIP may prevent mitochondrial apoptosis

4. Other Potential Solutions

Newer clinical trials are being done to understand if certain drugs may improve outlook for individuals with LADA. Two possible solutions are to increase insulin sensitivity and increase beta cell mass. Ramirez et al. found from a randomized clinical trial that sildenafil has the potential to increase insulin sensitivity in pre-diabetes²⁴. According to previous studies, researchers found that high blood sugar can cause the human body to produce a protein called thioredoxin interacting protein (TXNIP) [23, 25]. In fact TXNIP plays such a significant role that it plays a role in β -cell microRNA expression, β -cell function, and insulin production [26]. In the presence of diabetes this protein is increased. Verapamil was found to lower TXNIP and in mouse models and completely remove diabetes from them [27-28]. Additionally, TXNIP is found to cause carotid intima-media thickness in individuals with impaired glucose tolerance [29].

The autoimmune component of LADA and Type 1 Diabetes may not be exclusive to these conditions. Researchers are finding growing evidence that suggests chronic inflammation along with both adaptive and innate immunity may play a role in the evolution of Type 2 diabetes [30]. There is a close connection between how adipose tissue acquires immunogenicity and visceral adipose tissue begin to interact with B and T-cells. In the rat model, researchers have demonstrated how modulating B-cell function can reverse Type 2 diabetes [31]. This modulation suggests how biological DMARDS may be a future mainstay therapy for Type 2 Diabetes as well.

5. Conclusion

As the studies have revealed, traditional diagnosis methods and treatment protocol does not apply for LADA [32-35]. Novel approaches must be utilized in order to effectively treat the challenging components of this disorder. While sulfonylurea works effects for Type II diabetes, the same

treatment does not work for LADA [36-38]. Consequently increased awareness and change in treatment with biologic DMARD agents may prove to be a solution for this sub-population. Other forms of immunomodulation may be necessary in order to effectively treat LADA. This paradigm shift requires proper diagnosis and widespread recognition of this specific form of disease [39-40]

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